

Methodological approaches to assessing the efficiency of an enterprise in the context of economic security

The subject of the research is methodological approaches to assessing the efficiency of an enterprise in the context of economic security.

The aim of the research is to determine the methodological basis for assessing the efficiency of the enterprise in the context of economic security.

Research methods. The following methods were used in the study of the topic: financial analysis; economic analysis; systematic approach; risk assessment; economic security assessment; strategic management; PEST analysis; socio-economic; graphical and tabular methods, etc.

Results of the investigation. It is established that the assessment of enterprise performance in the context of economic security is due to the current challenges faced by enterprises in the context of globalization and an unstable economic environment. Performance evaluation is not only an indicator of enterprise success, but also an important tool for maintaining economic security. Effective resource management, financial stability, ability to adapt to changes in the external environment and minimize risks contribute to the economic security of the enterprise. The efficiency of an enterprise is a key factor in its stable development and competitiveness in the market. Assessing the efficiency of an enterprise is of particular importance in the context of increased global competition and economic turbulence. The economic security of an enterprise is defined as the state of protection of its resources, capital, information and other assets from threats that may arise both within the enterprise and externally. Methodological approaches to assessing enterprise performance are divided into the following groups: financial, operational, organizational and strategic. Evaluation of the enterprise's performance in the context of economic security is based on the basic principles, the use of which provides a comprehensive analysis of the enterprise's condition in terms of its financial, economic, production, innovation and social indicators. Evaluating the efficiency of an enterprise in the context of economic security is a complex process that takes into account many factors that can be classified into internal and external, as well as quantitative and qualitative. Each of these factors requires systematic monitoring and analysis to ensure the economic security of the enterprise and achieve its efficiency. Integration of financial, operational, organizational and strategic approaches to evaluation allows to create a comprehensive model of analysis.

Scope of the results. Enterprise economics, competitiveness, economic security, enterprise management, enterprise performance.

Conclusions. As a result, we have proved that methodological approaches to assessing the efficiency of an enterprise in the context of economic security are an important element of management practice, where the integration of financial, operational, organizational and strategic approaches allows for a deeper and more comprehensive analysis that increases the ability of an enterprise to withstand threats and strengthens its economic security. It is established that to ensure the sustainable development of an enterprise, it is necessary to regularly monitor its efficiency and introduce modern methods of analysis that take into account the dynamics of internal and external changes. It is determined that the efficiency of an enterprise is determined not only by financial indicators, but also by its ability to maintain stable development, adapt to changes in the market environment, reduce risks and ensure economic security. Thus, modern methodological approaches to assessing the performance of an enterprise should be flexible, integrated and focused on the long-term sustainability and security of an enterprise in a dynamic market environment, which will contribute not only to improving performance but also to ensuring reliable economic security, which is a key condition for the successful functioning of any enterprise in today's turbulent environment.

Keywords: evaluation, enterprise activity, efficiency, economic security, conditions of turbulence, sustainable development, methodological approaches, principles, factors.

Методичні підходи до оцінювання ефективності діяльності підприємства в контексті економічної безпеки

Предметом дослідження є методичні підходи до оцінювання ефективності діяльності підприємства в контексті економічної безпеки.

Метою дослідження є визначення методичних основ щодо оцінювання ефективності діяльності підприємства в контексті економічної безпеки.

Методи дослідження. При дослідженні теми було використано методи: фінансового аналізу; економічного аналізу; системного підходу; оцінки ризиків; оцінки економічної безпеки; стратегічного управління; PEST-аналізу; соціально-економічні; графічний та табличний методи та ін.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що оцінювання ефективності діяльності підприємства в контексті економічної безпеки обумовлена сучасними викликами, з якими стикаються підприємства в умовах глобалізації та нестабільного економічного середовища. Оцінка ефективності діяльності є не лише показником успішності підприємства, але й важливим інструментом для підтримки економічної безпеки. Ефективне управління ресурсами, фінансова стійкість, здатність адаптуватися до змін зовнішнього середовища та мінімізувати ризики сприяє підвищенню рівня економічної безпеки підприємства. Ефективність діяльності підприємства є ключовим чинником його стабільного розвитку та конкурентоспроможності на ринку. Оцінка ефективності діяльності підприємства набуває особливого значення в умовах посиленої глобальної конкуренції та економічної турбулентності. Економічна безпека підприємства визначається як стан захищеності його ресурсів, капіталу, інформації та інших активів від загроз, що можуть виникнути як всередині підприємства, так і зовні. Методичні підходи до оцінювання ефективності підприємства поділяються на такі групи: фінансові, операційні, організаційні та стратегічні. Оцінювання ефективності діяльності підприємства в контексті економічної безпеки базується на основних принципах, використання яких забезпечує всебічний аналіз стану підприємства з точки зору його фінансово-економічних, виробничих, інноваційних та соціальних показників. Оцінювання ефективності діяльності підприємства в контексті економічної безпеки – це комплексний процес, який враховує багато чинників, які можуть бути класифіковані на внутрішні та зовнішні, а також на кількісні та якісні. Кожен з цих чинників вимагає систематичного моніторингу та аналізу для забезпечення економічної безпеки підприємства і досягнення його ефективності. Інтеграція фінансових, операційних, організаційних та стратегічних підходів до оцінювання дозволяє створити комплексну модель аналізу.

Галузь застосування результатів. Економіка підприємства, конкурентоспроможність, економічна безпека, управління підприємствами, ефективність діяльності підприємства.

Висновки. В результаті нами було доведено, що методичні підходи до оцінки ефективності діяльності підприємства в контексті економічної безпеки є важливим елементом управлінської практики, де інтеграція фінансових, операційних, організаційних та стратегічних підходів дозволяє забезпечити більш глибокий і комплексний аналіз, що підвищує здатність підприємства протистояти загрозам і зміцнює його економічну безпеку. Встановлено, що для забезпечення стійкого розвитку підприємства необхідно регулярно проводити моніторинг його ефективності та впроваджувати сучасні методики аналізу, що враховують динаміку внутрішніх та зовнішніх змін. Визначено, що ефективність підприємства визначається не тільки фінансовими показниками, а й його здатністю підтримувати стабільний розвиток, адаптуватися до змін у ринковому середовищі, знижувати ризики і забезпечувати економічну безпеку. Таким чином, сучасні методичні підходи до оцінювання ефективності діяльності підприємства повинні бути гнучкими, інтегрованими та орієнтованими на довгострокову стійкість і безпеку підприємства в умовах динамічного ринкового середовища, що сприятиме не лише підвищенню результативності діяльності, але й забезпеченню надійної економічної безпеки, яка є ключовою умовою успішного функціонування будь-якого підприємства в сучасних умовах турбулентності.

Ключові слова: оцінювання, діяльність підприємства, ефективність, економічна безпека, умови турбулентності, стійкий розвиток, методичні підходи, принципи, чинники.

Formulation of the problem. The importance and relevance of assessing enterprise performance in the context of economic security is due to the current challenges faced by enterprises in the context of globalization and an unstable economic environment. In today's economy, where high levels of competition, technological innovation, and market volatility play a key role, the efficiency of an enterprise directly affects its sustainability and ability to withstand threats. Performance evaluation is not only an indicator of a company's success, but also an important tool for maintaining economic security. Effective resource management, financial stability, ability to adapt to changes in the external environment and minimize risks contribute to the economic security of the enterprise. Given the constant threats, such as crises, wars, inflation, exchange rate volatility and political risks, enterprises must have effective mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating their performance, which allows them to identify weaknesses and adjust strategies in a timely manner to ensure long-term competitiveness and economic stability. Thus, studying and improving methods for assessing the efficiency of an enterprise is an important management tool for improving economic security, which makes the issue relevant for scientific research and practical solutions in the context of modern economic instability.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The issue of assessing the efficiency of an enterprise in the context of economic security is relevant for both Ukrainian and foreign scholars. Among domestic authors, this problem has been studied: G. Kozachenko and O. Volk, who studied approaches to ensuring the economic security of enterprises by assessing the efficiency of the enterprise through the prism of risks and threats. L. Shtanko – studied the methodology for assessing the economic security of the enterprise and the role of financial indicators in this context. I. Blank is one of the leading Ukrainian experts in the field of financial management, whose works cover the financial aspects of economic security of enterprises. V. Kudryavtsev – focused on risk management as the basis of economic security of the enterprise. Among foreign authors, the works of: M. Porter, who studied competitive strategy and developed a model of competitive forces that affect the economic sustainability and security of enterprises. R.

Daft, whose work in the field of organizational management includes research on the efficiency of enterprises in terms of risk management. J. Stiglitz described the problematic issues of risks and economic security at different levels of the economy, including enterprises. R. Kaplan and D. Norton – developed the Balanced Scorecard methodology, which allows to evaluate the performance of enterprises, taking into account various aspects, including risks and security. N. Negroponte – studied how technology affects the economic security of enterprises. These and other authors have made a significant scientific contribution to the study of economic security and efficiency of enterprises, which allows us to form modern approaches to assessing these aspects in practice.

Presenting main material. The efficiency of an enterprise is a key factor in its stable development and competitiveness in the market. Assessing the efficiency of an enterprise is of particular importance in the context of increased global competition and economic turbulence. In the context of ensuring the economic security of an enterprise, the development of methodological approaches to performance evaluation is an important task. The economic security of an enterprise is defined as the state of protection of its resources, capital, information and other assets from threats that may arise both within the enterprise and externally. The main components of economic security of an enterprise are (Fig. 1) [1; 5; 8; 12; 13; 16; 20]:

Economic security directly depends on the efficiency of the enterprise, because the higher the level of efficiency, the more opportunities for protecting the enterprise from threats. Methodological approaches to assessing the efficiency of an enterprise can be divided into several main groups: financial, operational, organizational and strategic (Fig. 2) [2; 4; 7; 11; 13; 18; 20]. Each of these approaches has its advantages and disadvantages, which should be taken into account during the analysis.

The first main approach is financial, which includes financial performance indicators, which remain a key tool for assessing the performance of an enterprise. The main financial indicators include:

- return on assets (ROA) – shows how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate profit;
- return on equity (ROE) – characterizes the return on shareholders' investments;

Fig. 1. The main components of economic security

• net profit is an absolute indicator that reflects the financial result of the company's activities;

liquidity and solvency – assesses the ability of a company to meet its financial obligations.

Financial indicators allow for a quantitative analysis of the company's performance, but they do not always take into account the specifics of the industry and external risks.

The second methodological approach is operational. Operational performance indicators allow assessing the effectiveness of the company's internal processes, namely:

- labor productivity – the amount of output produced per unit of time or per employee;
- asset turnover – the rate at which the company uses its resources to achieve results;
- cost of production – determines how efficiently resources are used for production.

These indicators allow assessing the efficiency of the use of enterprise resources, but they may be less relevant for companies operating in the service or innovation sector.

The third approach is organizational. The efficiency of the enterprise largely depends on its organizational structure and human resources management, where the main indicators include:

- indicators of employee engagement and motivation;
- staff turnover;
- level of employees' qualification;
- the degree of implementation of the company's plans and strategies.

Organizational indicators allow assessing the quality of the company's management and its ability to adapt to changes.

The fourth approach is strategic. Assessment of strategic efficiency allows to evaluate the com-

Fig. 2. Methodical approaches to assessing enterprise efficiency

Table 1. Key factors influencing the assessment of efficiency in the context of economic security

№	Group	Indicators
1.	Financial factors	Solvency is the ability of a company to meet its financial obligations on time. Asset liquidity is the ability to quickly convert assets into cash without losing their value. Profitability is an indicator of the company's profitability, which indicates the efficiency of resource use. Financial stability is the balance between the company's own and borrowed resources.
2.	Production factors	Labor productivity is the efficiency of using labor to produce products or provide services. Technological innovations – the level of introduction of new technologies that affect production efficiency and competitiveness. Condition of equipment – depreciation or modernization of production facilities affects production efficiency and cost reduction. Energy efficiency – the impact of energy costs on the total cost of production.
3.	Personnel factors	Staff qualifications – the level of professional training of employees, which directly affects the quality and speed of work. Staff turnover – high staff turnover has a negative impact on business stability and development. Staff motivation – the degree of interest of employees in achieving the company's goals, which can increase productivity.
4.	Market factors	Competition – the presence of strong competitors can reduce market share and force the company to adapt its strategies. Demand for products or services – the company's dependence on market demand and the ability to respond quickly to its changes. Changes in raw material prices – fluctuations in the cost of resources can significantly affect production costs.
5.	Legal and regulatory factors	Legislative regulation – compliance with regulations and the existence of risks of changes in legislation. Tax pressure – the level of tax payments and the complexity of the taxation system may affect the financial stability of the company. Environmental requirements – the company must comply with environmental regulations, which affects its costs and reputation.
6.	Economic factors	Inflation – rising prices for goods and services reduce purchasing power and affect the company's overall revenue. Currency fluctuations – for businesses that operate in foreign markets or use imported materials, currency fluctuations can have a significant impact on financial results. Economic instability – the general state of the economy (recessions, crises) affects the demand and financial performance of the company.
7.	Social factors	Social responsibility – the company's reputation in the eyes of society and customers may affect demand and competitiveness. The level of social stability in the region – social conflicts or instability can disrupt the company's business processes.
8.	Innovative and technical factors	Research and development (R&D) – investments in innovations ensure a long-term increase in the company's efficiency and competitiveness. Information security – ensuring data protection and confidentiality can reduce the risks to the company's operations.
9.	Political factors	Political stability – the presence or absence of political risks in a country or region can significantly affect the company's operations. Government support programs – participation in government initiatives can have a positive impact on business development.
10.	Security factors	Financial security – protection of the company from the risks of bankruptcy or inability to fulfill obligations. Information security – protection of the company's information resources from cyberattacks and unauthorized access. Operational risks – control and management of risks associated with production processes, logistics, supply and other operational areas.

pany's ability to develop and sustain in the market over the long term. Strategic indicators include:

- level of innovation;

- level of competitiveness;
- level of strategic risk management;
- investment attractiveness of the enterprise.

These indicators allow not only to assess current performance but also to predict future growth and development of the enterprise.

Assessment of the enterprise’s performance in the context of economic security is based on the basic principles, the use of which provides a comprehensive analysis of the enterprise’s condition in terms of its financial, economic, production, innovation and social indicators:

- principle of comprehensiveness – taking into account all aspects of the company’s activities and their interrelationships;

- principle of dynamism – constant updating of estimates in accordance with changes in the external and internal environment of the enterprise;
- principle of reliability – use of reliable and verified data for analysis;
- principle of objectivity – performance evaluation based on objective criteria and indicators;
- principle of continuity – continuous monitoring of the company’s activities for timely identification of risks and threats.

Evaluating the performance of an enterprise in the context of economic security is a complex pro-

Fig. 3. Comprehensive model for analyzing the evaluation of enterprise efficiency in the context of integration of methodological approaches

cess that takes into account many factors that can be classified into internal and external, as well as quantitative and qualitative.

The key factors that influence the assessment of efficiency in the context of economic security are shown in Table 1 [3; 6; 7; 9; 14; 17; 19]:

Each of these factors requires systematic monitoring and analysis to ensure the economic security of the enterprise and achieve its efficiency. Assessment of enterprise efficiency in the context of economic security should take into account a wide range of factors and indicators. Integration of financial, operational, organizational and strategic approaches to evaluation allows to create a comprehensive model of analysis (Fig. 3) [10; 12; 15; 20].

Conclusions

Thus, we have proved that methodological approaches to assessing the efficiency of an enterprise in the context of economic security are an important element of management practice, where the integration of financial, operational, organizational and strategic approaches allows for a deeper and more comprehensive analysis that increases the ability of an enterprise to withstand threats and strengthens its economic security. It is established that in order to ensure the sustainable development of an enterprise, it is necessary to regularly monitor its efficiency and introduce modern methods of analysis that take into account the dynamics of internal and external changes. It is determined that the efficiency of an enterprise is determined not only by financial indicators, but also by its ability to maintain stable development, adapt to changes in the market environment, reduce risks and ensure economic security.

The authors establish that methodological approaches to performance assessment should include quantitative and qualitative indicators reflecting financial stability, production productivity, technological development, social aspects, and market competitiveness. An important role in the assessment process is also played by the analysis of risks related to economic security, including financial, legal, innovative and operational threats. Thus, modern methodological approaches to assessing the efficiency of an enterprise should be flexible, integrated and focused on the long-term sustainability and security of an enterprise in a dynamic market environment, which will contribute

not only to improving performance but also to ensuring reliable economic security, which is a key condition for the successful functioning of any enterprise in today's turbulent environment.

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